

Supplemental Materials

Loading enhances glucose uptake in muscles, bones, and bone marrow of lower extremities in humans

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Figure S1. Absolute glucose uptake (GU) in different regions from no load visit. GU sorted from highest to lowest absolute GU. The figure illustrates the high GU in vertebrae compared to other tissues without any respect to loading. Columns are colour coded after tissue type in different shades of grey: darkest grey = vertebral body bone marrow, dark grey = diaphyseal bone marrow region, medium grey = brown adipose tissue (BAT), light grey = muscles, lightest grey = white adipose tissue, white = cortical bone. SAT = subcutaneous adipose tissue. VAT = visceral adipose tissue. Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM. ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparisons test, comparing the thoracic vertebral GU with the GU in the other 16 evaluated tissues. *** $p < 0.001$ vs. GU in thoracic vertebrae.

Figure S2. Effect of increased loading on absolute glucose uptake (GU) in (A) Cortical bone in the long bones, (B) diaphyseal bone marrow region in the long bones. (C) Extremity located muscles and (D) subcutaneous adipose tissue in the region of femur, tibia, or humerus. P-values (high load vs no load) are calculated using paired samples T-test. Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM. * $p < 0.05$.

Glucose Uptake - Trunk Tissues

Figure S3. Effect of increased loading on absolute glucose uptake in trunk tissues. Increased weight-loading does not significantly affect GU in vertebral bodies, brown adipose tissue (BAT), visceral adipose tissue (VAT) or subcutaneous adipose tissue (SAT). Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM.